

Virtual Workshop:
Secure processing of health data
EOSC and EHDS approaches and synergies

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4th February 2025

www.elixir-europe.org

Trusted Research Environments (TRE) or Secure Data Environment (SDE) - UK NHS or Secure Processing Environment (SPE) - TEHDAS

(follows Office of UK National Statistics "five safes" principles)

A sustainable infrastructure for biological data

ELIXIR Members

ELIXIR Observers

1+Million Genomes initiative

“

1+MG facilitates countries to realise a practice of personalised medicine and health, based upon a shared 'trust framework' and the infrastructure to safely access and integrate high quality genomic data and other health data across borders

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The implementation of 1+Million Genomes

Cross-border access to genomic data, implementation of genomics-based health

2018

2020

2022

2024

2026

European
Genomic Data
Infrastructure

Federation of human genomic data

Many national datasets from human research participants needs to be **stored locally** (European Genome phenome Archive – EGA)

ELIXIR developing a federation with shared metadata (FAIR) and local data store (secure). Based on suite of interoperable, reusable, adopted, and fit-for-purpose **standards**

Linking local EGA to national clouds and international access (ELIXIR-AAI - Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure)

17/25 ELIXIR Nodes are funded in the FHD community

Use case: COVID-19

Beacon and the ELIXIR Beacon Network

A **Beacon** allows an **anonymous query** to see if a **dataset contains a genome** with a **given base** at a **particular coordinate**, with a simple **yes/no response**

- 24-month project, 10 ELIXIR Nodes
- Aim: disseminate the Beacon and ELIXIR Beacon Network

The **ELIXIR Beacon Network (EBN)** enables **human data discovery** from **European data resources**

- 24-month project, 9 ELIXIR Nodes
- Aim: engagement to ensure relevance for the biomedical community

EOSC-ENTRUST

Aims:

1. Create a European **network of trusted research environments** for sensitive data
2. Drive European interoperability by joint development of a **common blueprint** for federated data access and analysis.

Start date: **1 March 2024**

End date: **28 February 2027**

EU contribution: **€4.2M**

Coordinated by: **ELIXIR**

Project partners: **34**

ENTRUST = **E**uropean **N**etwork of **TRUST**ed Research Environments

European data spaces

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Thank you

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